

PROJECT COMMUNICATION PLAN

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Euro-Argo Research Infrastructure Sustainability and Enhancement
Project (EA RISE Project) - 824131

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Accepted by	C. GOURCUFF

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1 Introduction

Euro-Argo provides open and free ocean data to a variety of users, including researchers and operational forecasting centres. Argo data are provided to users both in real time and in delayed mode after careful analysis of the data quality and potential correction by specialists, thus targeting different user categories. The development of Euro-Argo extensions towards high latitudes, in European marginal seas, towards biogeochemistry and deeper measurements will be implemented in Euro-Argo RISE H2020 project and will give access to new types of data and new potential users.

This document presents the Project Communication Plan, e.g communication goals and the types of actions foreseen for ensuring the proper visibility of the project and its achievements among main target audiences.

2 Scope and objectives

2.1 Scope

The Euro-Argo RISE (EA RISE) Communication Plan is a public deliverable which corresponds to the deliverable D7.1, produced in the context of WP7. WP7 is a transverse work package, whose objectives are both to enhance the visibility of the Euro-Argo network in order to attract new users and raise awareness among all stakeholders, and to strengthen link with existing users and better answering their needs. This work package also includes a task (7.5) dedicated to the communication of EA RISE results. As part of this task, the EA RISE **Project Communication Plan** (PCP) defines how the projects outcomes will be disseminated and communicated to different communities of stakeholders. The document defines key objectives, identifies the target audiences, proposes tools that best suit the needs of these groups, indicate responsibilities for the planned actions, and outlines indicators to assess the impact of the strategy.

2.2 Objectives

The dissemination and communication project activities mainly aim **at maximising the Euro-Argo RISE visibility** by:

- Raising awareness of project's objectives, results, benefits, use and applicability through diverse channels to all interested parties,
- Promoting a deeper understanding of data access to users community and new users,
- Attracting new users and,
- Enhancing Euro-Argo visibility towards the general public, educational communities and policy makers

Communication, defined by informing about project and results, and dissemination, *i.e* describing and making results available for use, will be followed through:

- one-way channels (mass media communication):
 - communicating on the Euro-Argo RISE activities and disseminating the main scientific and data management outcomes of the project;
 - participating to and organizing events for, (1) a wide audience locally, nationally and internationally, and (2), a specialized audience (researchers, data users, manufacturers, SMEs...).
- two-ways channels (interpersonal communication):
 - outreaching with schools, students, young researchers;
 - training technical teams and potential users thus easing the access to materials and data.

3 Target audience

3.1 Argo user communities

3.1.1 Current users

Argo user communities are well defined and exist for more than 20 years at the European level. It consists in:

- Research community
- Operational oceanography
- Technical operators of the infrastructure

3.1.2 New users

Several activities will be performed to promote the potential of Argo data and attract new users.

New variables will be implemented and geographical areas extended during the project by engaging with countries surrounding the European seas: new members will hopefully join the Argo community.

These new potential users will come from various countries and from different areas of ocean and climate research (physics, biogeochemistry...), operational oceanography, technical operators of the infrastructure, but also from industry.

3.2 Other key stakeholders: Policy makers

It is essential that other key stakeholders including policy makers are aware of the project, its results, its benefits, their use and applicability.

Indeed, they will influence future standards and support future developments so it is important that they contribute to making this Argo new phase a recognized reference for global ocean observational systems.

3.3 Private sector / SMEs

Fostering the link with private sector to improve technological and scientific developments is also important, in order to allow technology transfer. Development and improvement of the instruments and sensors will help to better understand the oceans and answer new societal challenges and scientific needs.

3.4 General Public

General public involves all non-specialist stakeholders with particular interests/needs such as environmental NGOs, citizen organizations, students and individual citizens. It is important to increase public awareness on the role of the ocean in the global environment.

The activities results will be disseminated to the society at large in such a way that they can be understood by non-specialists. Communication of results towards the general public will be done in a concerted way through the media department of the different partners.

3.5 Educational community (Ocean Observers)

We will lean on the Ocean Observers network as ambassador of Educational world. This network is composed by ocean scientists (young researchers...), educators, and marine communicators willing to:

- provide a clear message to the future citizens: expressing a precise and rigorous scientific message and exciting stories about maintaining, exploiting and improving an operational network of autonomous platforms in the entire Ocean
- stimulate interest in youth audience and
- attract future scientists in the broad fields of marine sciences.

The Ocean Observers will serve as a platform to raise awareness of the importance of the ocean observation for human life to young generations.

4 Communication and dissemination tools

Any communication and dissemination outputs related to Euro-Argo RISE and any major results funded by Euro-Argo RISE will i) display the EU emblem (<http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/>) and ii) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824131.”

Furthermore, any dissemination/communication activity related to Euro-Argo RISE will indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.1 Events

4.1.1 Organization of workshops.

Workshops help to establish and enhance partnerships. A total of 10 workshops/events involving different kind of stakeholders are planned within the project:

- Expanding the Argo user community: organization of 2 Euro-Argo users workshop to allow cross fertilization of science (1st: October 2019 and 2nd: 2021).
 - Leader: EA ERIC
 - Conveners: All partners
- Sharing and gathering experiences on ocean observing educational activities: One educational workshop (Ocean Observer Workshop - May/June 2020)
 - Leader: JCOMMOPS / EA ERIC
 - Conveners: HCMR, SU, SOCIB, MI
- The event jointly organised with other ocean observing networks should be hold aside off the EuroGOOS Conference (2020) or at EGU - D8.3.
 - Leader: HCMR (task 8.1)
 - Conveners: IPMA, IEO, MI, SOCIB
- One political event around marginal Seas: for stakeholders and Politics (organized aside of the IOC meeting, in June 2021) – D6.7
 - Leader: OGS (lead of Deliverable), event organized by IO-BAS
 - Conveners:
 - Conveners from Baltic Sea : IO-BAS,FMI, IO PAN, IMR
 - Conveners from Mediterranean Sea: HCMR, SOCIB, SU, IEO
- One Baltic & Artic workshop: Regional scale (Autumn 2020) – D6.6 + D5.2
 - Leader: IO PAN with the help of FMI
 - Conveners: IMR, BSH
- One Mediterranean & Black Seas workshop: Regional scale (2021 – aside the 2nd user workshop) - D6.5:
 - Leader: HCMR (lead of Deliverable)
 - Conveners: OGS, IO-BAS, SOCIB, SU, IEO, JCOMMOPS

- Two DMQC training workshops (2020 and 2022) (task 2.4)
 - Leader: IFREMER (WP2 leader)
 - Conveners: IEO, FMI, OGS, NERC, BSH, SOCIB (task 2.4 participants + WP3 partners)

- One workshop to improve interaction with industry and SMEs: special sessions on technology from industrial users and with manufacturers will facilitate engagement with industry to enhance the instruments and sensors. Event could be organized during “Ocean Business” (Southampton, Spring 2021) or “Oceanology” Conference (March 2020 or 2022) – D8.1.
 - Leader: NERC-NOC
 - Conveners: EA ERIC, SU, MI, SOCIB

Figure 1: Summary of the planned timeline for EA RISE events & workshops, as defined during the first Executive Board meeting. This timeline will be updated during the project.

4.1.2 Participation at events

- Presentations (oral and poster):
 Examples: Presentations of the project outcomes to Argo Community (Argo Steering Team, Argo Data Management Team meetings), to marine science community (EGU, Ocean Science...)

Leader: EA ERIC

Partner: All EA RISE participants

4.2 Website applications

4.2.1 Project website

A section on the Euro-Argo website dedicated to Euro-Argo RISE has been set up (<https://www.euro-argo.eu/EU-Projects/Euro-Argo-RISE-2019-2022>);

The website constitutes a key communication tool to increase project visibility and impact towards industrial communities, researchers and general public. After the official end of the project, the foreground of the project will still be accessible and available for all interested parties as it will be hosted on Euro-Argo website.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.3 Social media

The official hashtag #EARISE was chosen for the project on Twitter and is already in use.

This hashtag was used for the announcement of the Kick Off Meeting in January and will be connected to all partners Twitter accounts. This project tag will be maintained allowing the entire project community to follow-up the latest project developments.

Figure 2: Twitter account for EA RISE

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.4 Printed and digital materials

4.4.1 Project identity

Logo was designed to keep the Euro-Argo brand in the Euro-Argo RISE logo as important to keep linked to Euro-Argo ERIC. This work on logo and template documents with a common graphic charter started on March 2019 and was finalized in April 2019. Logo will be displayed on each communication outputs and will establish a recognized Euro-Argo RISE style.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.4.2 Brochures and posters

A range of printed and digital materials (brochures, posters, etc.) that reflects Euro-Argo RISE identity (see above) will be developed. The content of these resources will be tailored to specific audiences and/or the type of dissemination activity e.g. conference, exhibition etc.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.4.3 Euro-Argo Newsletters

Main outcomes of the project will be disseminated through Euro-Argo newsletter, three times a year. These newsletters will allow the information of Euro-Argo members and observers of the main progress of the project.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.4.4 Educational material shared within the Ocean Observers community

These educational materials are constituted by online games, courses, etc. related to ocean observations, including some of the material directly related to Argo (e.g. "Adopt a float" initiative) and some directly participating in the promotion of EA RISE results (eg. "Wesstiti" game for Argo floats in western boundary currents). These materials will enrich the education section of the Euro-Argo website, through the provision of web links.

Leader: EA ERIC & JCOMMOPS

Partners: SU, HCMR, MI, SOCIB

4.5 Journal articles and publications

- **Peer reviewed publication in scientific journals**

Members of the EA RISE consortium will be encouraged to publish papers/articles in peer reviewed journals and other suitable publications to disseminate project results as widely as possible.

Each publication will mention the EU's funding origin as stated at the beginning of paragraph 4. Communication and dissemination tools.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.6 Mainstream Media

Mainstream media (*i.e.* television, radio, newspapers, magazines) shall be conceived as additional venues for the promotion of the project objectives and results. It addresses mainly other key stakeholders and general public.

Interactions with press (ex: newspapers articles, press releases...) will be explored in order to present important news about the project, as warranted by progress of the project.

Leader: EA ERIC

Partners: All EA RISE participants

4.7 Summary of target groups and related channels

Table 1: Euro-Argo RISE target groups and related channels

CHANNELS	TARGET GROUPS				
	Argo users community	Other Key stakeholders: policy makers	Private sector / SMEs	General public	Educational world (Ocean Observers Community)
Events	X	X	X		X (Only Ocean Observers Workshop)
Website application	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X	X
Printed and digital materials:					
<i>Brochures & Posters</i>	X	X	X		X
<i>Newsletters</i>	X	X	X		X
<i>Educational material</i>	X			X	X
Journal articles and publications	X		X		
Mainstream media		X	X	X	X

5 Impacts

Success of the communication and dissemination activities will be evaluated every 18 months for the periodic report to the EC, based on indicators defined in the table below.

Table 2: Selected indicators for the monitoring of communication and dissemination tools

Indicators
EVENTS
Organised Events
Number of events organized
Number of attendees
Attended Events
Number of oral communications and posters at congresses/events
WEBSITE APPLICATIONS
Number of monthly visits
Traffic acquisition
Duration of visits
SOCIAL MEDIA (Twitter)
#EARISE numbers (Number of time the project hashtag was tweeted & retweeted)
JOURNAL ARTICLES AND PUBLICATIONS
Number of submitted scientific papers in open access journals
MAINSTREAM MEDIA
Number of press articles

6 Synthesis

